

THE IMPORTANCE OF THE DEVELOPMENT OF DISTANCE LEARNING TODAY

Saidqosimov Islom

Student of Jizzakh branch of the National University of Uzbekistan
Jizzakh, Uzbekistan

Abstract: *The attention paid to the education system in our country today requires a lot of practical work. Distance learning at every stage of the education system involves increasing their effectiveness. To do this, it is necessary to create a variety of classrooms that use information technology to facilitate the exchange of educational information through a distance learning environment and to facilitate the acquisition of knowledge and skills to conduct and manage the learning process.*

Keywords— Distance education, information, technology, modern education, distance learning methods, multimedia programs.

1. INTRODUCTION

Distance education is a type of education organized through the use of information and telecommunications in education. In distance education systems, the quality and relevance of knowledge should be a priority. Distance learning differs from traditional forms of education. In distance learning, teachers need to pay close attention not only to the content of the course, but also to the form in which it is taught. When creating distance learning resources, it is necessary to take into account the tools for their online use, search engines, testing, self-study tools, distance learning in the laboratory.

Resolution of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated April 20, 2017 No PP-2909 "On measures to further develop the system of higher education" there was a new impetus for a radical revision.

2. MAIN PART

In order to solve such problems in the world practice, the opportunities of e-learning and distance learning based on the widespread use of information and communication technologies are

being used. If in the past some universities offered separate elements of e-learning and distance learning, for the last 6-7 years it has been offered en masse, using MOOC technologies. The Massive Open Online Course (MOOC - Massive Open Online Course) is a form of distance learning that offers free access to the Internet and interactive participation using e-learning technologies. In addition to traditional course materials, including video, reading, and homework, public open online courses allow students to participate in interactive forums that help build and support teams of teachers and assistants.

Popular open online courses appeared in the field of distance learning in 2008, but in 2012 projects such as Coursera, Udacity and Udemy became really popular after attracting the first investment. The first MOOC websites (Udacity, for example) mainly promoted the concept of access (open content). Later, the sites switched to paid content, leaving the opportunity to study for free, in whole or in part. Some platforms do not have their own content (educational materials), but they receive content from them in agreement with the world's leading universities. The obtained learning materials are easy for students to place on their platforms in a systematic manner.

Public courses based on the traditional model of distance education (clear schedule of the teaching process, course content, student supervision and certification) are an integral part of the MOOC - these are mainly free university courses. Public open online courses have been growing rapidly in recent years. However, our distance learning is still showing lower results than in other parts of the world.

Today's task of the education system is to teach students to work comfortably in a crowded information-educational environment. To do this, they need to create conditions for continuous independent work. The main purpose of distance learning, used in the training and retraining of teachers and researchers: to create opportunities for students to study in a voluntary educational institution around the world, regardless of where they live, using the potential of professors and teachers in educational institutions. Improving the quality of education, ensuring continuous learning for students and bringing different forms of education closer together.

The difference between the distance education system and the traditional form of education is its high mobility due to its flexibility, the large number of opportunities for students to work independently, the diversity of educational and methodological support, which depends on where the students are. This will increase the efficiency of the educational process.

The advantages of distance learning are: a creative learning environment. When teaching on the basis of traditional methods, the student reads only the given material. Based on the distance learning method, students will be able to search for the necessary information from the database and share their experiences with other students on the basis of electronic networks;

- the presence of significant changes in the workplace. Distance education provides a wide range of opportunities for millions of students, especially those who are inseparable from production;

- is a new and effective means of teaching and learning. Statistics show that distance learning is as effective as inpatient learning.

The advantage of students studying in this style is that they are provided with the best and quality didactic materials and potential speakers. In this style, students can "travel the world" via the INTERNET.

Thanks to our independence, we have the opportunity not only in our social life, but also in all the advanced countries of the world, the achievements of science and technology, the use of high-quality technical means, their creation. It serves to develop new computer technologies in various fields of production and to train mature specialists. I think that the role of teaching computer science and information technology is very important at a time when our society is developing.

3. CONCLUSION

In short, it is difficult to meet a person who is not interested in computer science and does not want to study it, so it is advisable to use new methods and forms in the education system. One of the most important needs today is to introduce them into the educational process and to teach them to students in practice. At the same time, the use of information and information technologies, the ability to master the mechanism of its work and its application in the learning process facilitates the learning process.

4. REFERENCES

- [1] Abduqodirov A.A., Hayitov A.G'. Beysik dasturlash tilidan test topshiriqlari. -T.,1999.– 60 b.
- [2] Azlarov T.R. Informatika va hisoblash texnikasi asoslari kursini milliy maktablarda o'qitishni takomillashtirishning metodik sistemasi. Ped. fan. nom. ... diss. -T., 1993. – 150 b.
- [3] Aripov M.M., Muhammadiyev J.O'. Informatika, informatsion texnologiyalar //Oliy o'quv yurtlari uchun darslik. –T.: TDYUI, 2004. –B. 275.